
SCAMPER TECHNIQUE: IN PERSPECTIVE OF RECENT TRENDS IN LIS PROFESSION

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.7160933

Abstract:

The advancement of information communication technology (ICT) is the core of the present techno-savvy era. ICT has transformed the field of information science through breakthroughs in academic communication, the paperless era, networking, and lifestyle changes. The significant shift in user demand simulates pivotal parts of efficient library services. As a result, ICT has changed the job of librarians to that of SMART librarians. Creative thinking means looking at something in a new way. The SCAMPER technique is one of the successful methods used in creative thinking. Adoption of SCAMPER technique will Make It Feasible For Libraries To Upgrade Services And Be In Line With Time And Technology.

Keywords: *Library Science, Information Science, Recent Trends, Creative Thinking, SCAMPER*

Prolog:

A fundamental of the Digital Era is the advancement of information communication technology (ICT). In the twenty-first century, the use of ICT in service sectors including banking, insurance, railroads, and aviation appears to be a widespread occurrence. Libraries are not exempt from this. As a result their services have been enhanced and expanded. “the wonders and innovations of technologies are being propagated in educational, social, political, and economic circles.”¹ (Ajidahun, 2007)

The five laws of library science put forward by Dr. S.R. Ranganathan serve as the cornerstone for efficient library services. Dr. S.R. Ranganathan presented these Five laws in the context of the book. The use of ICT in the modern era has led to a shift in users' demands from "book" to "piece of information." As a result, in the current digital age, the principle for effective library service shall be reformulated as follows:

- The piece of information is for use
- Every reader has his/her Piece of information.
- Every piece of information has its reader.

¹ Ajidahun C.O. (2007). The Development and Education of Library

Manpower in Information Technology in University Libraries In Nigeria. .

World libraries, 17(1), 44-66.

- Save the time of the reader and utilize the time of staff
- The Knowledge is a growing organism.

Thus presently due to significant shift in user's demand, it is essential to implement ICT tools in LIS profession. Eventually ICT is changing the profile of librarian from book provider to that of SMART librarians, databrian, information scientist etc. This article discusses use of SCAMPER technique to implement newfangled technologies in LIS in the techno Savvy Era.

What Is Creative Thinking?

Creative thinking means looking at something in a new way. It is the very definition of "thinking outside the box." Often, creativity in this sense involves what is called lateral thinking, or the ability to perceive patterns that are not obvious.

Scamper Technique:

The SCAMPER technique, for one, uses a set of directed, idea-spurring questions to suggest some addition to, or modification of, something that already exists.² (Serrat, 2017)

The SCAMPER technique is one of the successful methods used in creative thinking. The SCAMPER method is founded very simply on the theory that what is new is essentially a modification of existing, old things around itself. During brainstorming sessions, Bob Eberle first proposed the SCAMPER technique to address specific queries that aid in problem-solving or spark original thought. The seven techniques "Substitute, Combine, Adapt, Modify, Put to Another Use, Eliminate, and Reverse" make up the

acronym SCAMPER. These terms stand in for the critical issues that were discussed during the meeting for creative problem-solving.

Substitute:

The substitute technique is concerned with the components of the good, service, or solution that may be swapped out for another. Choosing whether to replace one step of the process with another is the main topic of discussion at this point.

Combine:

The combine technique examines the feasibility of combining two concepts, steps in a process, or outputs into a single, more effective result. Combining two creative concepts might occasionally result in a new product or technology that has a strong market position.

Adapt:

The term "adapt" describes a brainstorming session that tries to modify or improve a good or service. This modification might range from simple alterations to drastic changes to the entire project.

Modify:

The modify technique refers to modifying the system in a way that reveals greater creative potential or requires attention. Placing an emphasis on the entire process, this transformation goes beyond simple adjustment.

Put to other purpose:

This method focuses on finding new uses for the existing process or product as well as ways to address challenges with it. Anyone may use this strategy, for instance, to figure out how to adapt an existing product for a different market or user group.

Eliminate:

As the name suggests this technique aims to identify process components that can be eliminated to

² Serrat, O. (2017). The SCAMPER Technique. Knowledge Solutions, 312-314.

enhance the final product or service. Reviewing and eliminating the unnecessary components is essential in up gradation of a project or system.

Rearrange /Reverse:

The reverse or rearrange approach, which aims to explore the innovative possibilities while changing the sequence of the operation in the manufacturing line, is the final achievement technique. Reversing the process, in whole or in part, will facilitate in problem- solving or lead to more meaning-making.

The SCAMPER method, which stands for "Suggestion, Combination, Analysis, Adaptation, Modification, Put to other purposes, Elimination, and Reverse," is one of the most straightforward ways to stimulate creative thinking and problem-solving. These can be employed to tackle issues from seven different angles. This comprehensive research method aids in making the optimal option, which stimulates creative thinking and innovation.

Recent Trends In LIS Profession:

"Information and communication technology is the application of technologies consisting of hardware, software, network and media for collection, storage processing transmission and presentation of information in vocal,

textual, pictorial and multimedia formats"³ (Igwe, 2011)

ICT is an important and effective tool for achieving long-term growth in all parts of our society. ICT offers a way to achieve developmental objectives in a variety of fields, including business, agriculture, health, and education. Currently, the impact that ICT-driven globalization is remarkable in the library and information (LIS) profession. Libraries can use ICTs to locate, store, retrieve, and disseminate information. Libraries use ICT resources to disseminate information.

Library Computerization:

The use of computers to store and retrieve information in libraries is known as library computerization. There are several softwares widely available for Library Computerization. These programs help the library in procurement, cataloging, circulation, and serials control.

Library Automation:

Automation is a process of using machinery for easy working and saving human power and time. Library automation is the use of the machine for the collection, processing, storage, and retrieval of information. Library Automation offers to do routine work of the library with the help of machinery without human interference. ICT can be used to automate different traditional library activities such as acquisition, cataloging, circulation, stock verification, information retrieval, dissemination, etc. Library automation brings ease, speed, and promptness in information handling as well as accuracy in the work.

Hybrid Library:

Hybrid libraries are the digital version of conventional libraries, which

3 Igwe, K. (2011). Issues in the Automation of Libraries and information Centers. In R.A.J Imoh & K.N. Igwe (Eds.) Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Systems for Library Services. Wunmi: Commercial Press

also house traditional, fixed media holdings. They, therefore, include both paper and electronic resources.

Electronic or virtual libraries:

A digital library is a collection of digital information connected with e-services that build on the functions of a traditional library and allows worldwide access to its collection over the internet. The digital library is also known as a virtual library, an electronic library, a library without walls, and a mobile library. All of these phrases have been used equally to characterize the storage and dissemination of electronic information.

Institutional Repository:

Institutional repositories house local publications produced by the institute, including theses, dissertations, reports, conference papers, and seminar papers. An institutional repository is described as a database with a set of services to collect, store, index, preserve, and disseminate the research outputs of an institution in digital formats. ICT has made it possible to assure the preservation of content in addition to enhancing access to them.

Information retrieval center :

Modern information retrieval facilities organize, store, and provide access to both text-based and media-rich information sources. As a result, a modern library maintains a system for searching information from documents in its collection to fulfill its function as an information retrieval center.

Data Center:

A data center is a building that offers shared access to applications and data through a sophisticated network, compute, and storage infrastructure. It is an organization that houses information about a specific, specialized field of expertise from which services are provided.

In this technologically advanced age, a library may work as a data center to provide information in a specialist field and have data handling capabilities

Information hub:

The information hub is a portal to knowledge and culture. They provide services and resources that promote literacy, education, and learning opportunities. It aids in the shaping of fresh thoughts and ideas. With the advent of technology, libraries can now be transformed into informational hubs where people can avail self-learning.

Application of Web 3.0 for library services

Web 3.0 third generation of Internet-based services that collectively comprise what might be called 'The Intelligent Web' — such as those using semantic web, microformats, natural language search, data mining, machine learning, recommendation agents, and artificial intelligence technologies — which emphasize machine-facilitated understanding of information to provide a more productive and intuitive user experience.

Instant Messaging (IM), Wikis, Blogs or Weblogs, Streaming Media, RSS Feeds (Really Simple Syndication), Social Book Marking, Podcasts, Social Networking, and Tagging are just a few examples of Web 3.0 tools that can assist to deliver services to users more quickly and precisely. Further these tools are also helpful in sharing information (links, data, files, audio, and video clips), user education, promoting library services and events.

OPAC and WebOPAC:

Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) is the name of the computerized version of the library catalog. Web-based OPAC or web-based catalog is referred to as web OPAC. Thus it is an online

database of items that are kept by a library or collection of libraries and made accessible through the internet. Nowadays libraries are capable to provide global access to their catalogs via Web OPAC. As a result, library patrons have 24/7 access to information from around the world. Additionally, the Web OPAC provides links to other sources of information, such as tables of contents, full-text documents, author, title, publishers, publication year, etc.

Resource Sharing and Union Catalogue:

ICT can be used to exchange resources between libraries and information centers. ICT plays a vital role in the cooperative collection, storage, processing, and sharing of information. A union catalog may be more effectively administered through ICT by enabling libraries to develop and share digital bibliographic data and other information resources. It provides a great opportunity for libraries to share their resources with other libraries.

QR Code:

The Quick Response code (QR code) is a specific kind of 2D barcode. They are also referred to as Matrix codes, 2D codes, 2D barcodes, and mobile codes. QR code is capable of being decoded quickly, from any angle, or using any position-detection patterns. This technology of QR codes is commonly utilized to communicate with end users. Utilizing a QR code is quite easy. Libraries primarily implement QR codes to publicize their services. Today many libraries use the QR code technology to provide instant access to their resources to their users.

RFID Technology:

To improve the number of options for quick and user-friendly services libraries is now offering ICT-based library services.

New technology has altered the way libraries conduct transactions (check-in and check-out). An excellent invention "Radio Frequency Identification" technology is employed in libraries (RFID). Nowadays, Libraries are implementing RFID technology to deliver richer and more effective library services. The fourth law of library science, "save the time," is accomplished by this technique by offering prompt and efficient services, the users

Application Of Scamper Technique In LIS Profession:

SCAMPER technique can be used to provide quick and precise services to full fill five laws of library sciences defined by Dr. S.R. Ranganathan, Father of Library Science. It will make it possible to libraries to upgrade services and be in line with time and technology. Following is an example of how libraries can be shaped up in context with SCAMPER adopting recent trends in LIS profession.

SCAMPER	Questions to Ask	What Can Be changed	What can be used instead
Substitute	What could be used instead? What kind of alternate material Can I use?	Manual Database	Use of ICT in library
Combine	What could be added? How can I combine Purposes?	Manual work	Library Computerization, Library Automation, Digital Repository
Adapt	How can it be adjusted to fit another purpose? What else is like this?	Library Resources	Hybrid Library Virtual Library, Mobile Library, Information retrieval center
Modify	What happens if I exaggerate a component? How can it be made larger or stronger?	Library Services	Web 3.0 for library services
Put to other purpose	Who else might be able to use it? What else can it are used for other than its original purpose?	Book Circulation	Information retrieval center, Data Center, Information hub, self- learning center
Eliminate	What can be removed? or taken away from it? What can be expanded? or Developed more?	Traditional search	WebOPAC- Union Catalogue Resource Sharing
Rearrange	Can I interchange any Components? How can the layout? or pattern be changed?	Traditional System	RFID QR Code

Effectiveness Of Scamper Technique In LIS Profession:

The SCAMPER technique boosts inventive tactics to problem-solving and the generation of renewed perceptions based on the demands we pose to produce unexpected insights. One can use this technique in any sector to and resolve the issues and progression. Effectiveness of SCAMPER technique in LIS profession as follows:

1. This method is exclusively supportive for coming up with recent trends in this techno-savvy era.
2. This techniques will help to the libraries in resolve the issues and upgrade the system.

3. This method inspires to enhance current processes and services.
4. This technique assists to formulate speedy and pin point services by eliminating time consuming services and hence save the time of readers and library staff.
5. This method greatly assists the LIS profession in shaping the services in this cutting-edge technological era.
6. This method will assist LIS professionals to provide user centric services and achieve user's satisfaction by providing information in one click.
7. In this era of information explosion, the SCAMPER technique will aid LIS

professionals in upholding the values outlined in Dr. S.R. Ranganathan's Five Laws of Library Science.

Conclusion:

Presently in this ICT era every system and services need to upgrade and to align with customer's demands. The creating thinking is the methods which can be implemented in every sector for progress and problem solving. The SCAMPER technique is the one of the best technique in critical thinking. It allows systems to think in seven different perspectives. The SCAMPER technique is a systematic method of removing barriers from ideas, enabling the generation of fresh ideas and the creation of enhanced service and products. SCAMPER technique helps to LIS profession and experts to build the services that meet current needs. It will make possible to upgrade services by eliminating flaws from traditional services. Thus in today's savvy era implementation of SCAMPER technique is the ideal way of updating LIS services and boost the profession.

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